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FEMaLe**

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1 Introduction

The aim of Task 4.4 was to develop two experimental software programs (prototypes) for clinical decision support (CDS) for the individual patient:

1. A risk stratification tool that uses the genomic/genotypic disease signatures (defined as combinations of one or more SNP genotypes) to classify women into high and low risk for endometriosis.
2. An extension of the risk stratification tool with biological annotations, i.e. including the disease signatures' associated genes and biological mechanisms. Prepare the CDS product architecture for further extensions with non-genetic signatures (phenotypic and clinical data) with the potential to guide treatment of endometriosis.

We have integrated these two versions into a single prototype CDS tool, which is described in this document.

Our starting point for this work was clustering the endometriosis associated disease signatures identified by our combinatorial analysis of UK Biobank data based on the patients in which they co-occur. This high-resolution genetic architecture of the disease allowed us to identify SNPs, genes and genetic biomarkers that are potentially specific to different patient subgroups and the more clinically relevant genetic/mechanistic subgroups that make up the disease population.

When we have access to appropriate replication datasets and associated clinical data, we can further test the way they correlate with patients' phenotype and disease risk and evaluate their potential performance as mechanism-based patient stratification biomarkers (PSBs). These disease signatures are used as PSBs in the CDS tool to identify the likely mechanistic etiology of disease and the most likely effective therapy for patients.

2 Summary of Previous Results

The aim of Task 4.1 was to develop a workflow for discovery in UK Biobank (UKB) [1], replication in Copenhagen Hospital Biobank (CHB) [2], and patient risk scoring based on combinations of one or more SNP genotypes associated with endometriosis (disease signatures). We successfully implemented tools for testing each disease signature from UKB on the Danish CHB data.

In Task 4.2 using direct (non-imputed) genotypes only from 4,493 cases and 62,574 controls we identified 1,767 disease signatures of order 2-5 in UKB (**Table 1**). 364 disease signatures contained at least one of the genetic variants (single nucleotide polymorphisms, SNPs) associated with endometriosis from the recent genome-wide association study (GWAS) of endometriosis [3]. In total, 18 of 42 GWAS SNPs were identified within the combinations.

Table 1. Overview of the number of identified UK Biobank high-risk disease signatures for each order 2-5, and the associated endometriosis disease risk.

Order <i>n</i>	Number of disease signatures	Odds ratio range
2	200	1.25-3.99
3	412	1.41-5.78
4	457	1.76-7.78
5	686	2.08-13.54

Detailed work on evaluating the replication of the disease signatures found in UK Biobank in the Danish CHB dataset was undertaken by PrecisionLife, supported by our Danish partner. This has generated encouraging preliminary results, which have been analyzed in detail by PrecisionLife. However, this work was not able to be completed until very recently.

As the methodology used for evaluating replication is necessarily different between a combinatorial disease signature and a single SNP, and there has been no opportunity for the partners to discuss the statistical methodology or the thousands of signatures and extensive report of findings in detail, this work has not been presented in this final report. This will be the subject of ongoing and future work by PrecisionLife.

3 CDS Prototype

Unlike traditional Genome-Wide Association Studies (GWAS) that identify disease-associated (more specifically, case population-associated) single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and find single genes associated with disease, the PrecisionLife combinatorial analytics platform can identify disease-associated combinations of multi-modal genetic, clinical, and epidemiological factors. These combinations capture the non-linear effects of interactions between multiple genes and exogenous factors that contribute to disease risk for specific patient subgroups.

Rather than assuming that individual SNP genotypes have the same effect on phenotype in all patients and that all patients in the case population have the same overarching molecular aetiology, analysing networks of combinatorial disease signatures could allow us to identify subgroups of endometriosis patients that have shared genetic mechanisms [4]. We can then offer further insight into disease biology by testing whether individual patient subgroups are associated with distinct endometriosis phenotypes such as disease staging, symptom presentation and fertility status if such data are available.

3.1 Basic Requirements

For the CDS prototype, we selected 184 signatures and their 317 SNPs which have a p -value < 0.001 in the UKB and CHB analysis.

The primary goal of Task 4.4 was to implement a prototype clinical decision support (CDS) tool to report the risk profile of the individual patient, including their specific combinations of disease associated genes with clear and well-accepted biological mechanisms, to make the report explainable and actionable at the point of care. This is designed to report back the risk of a patient having endometriosis and its contributing mechanistic causes in that patient.

For this project we focused on the data available, i.e., the genetic profile (disease signatures consisting of one or more SNP genotypes) of the patients, but the PrecisionLife CDS platform is capable of including other kinds of data, for example proteomics, phenotypic or clinical features when they are available in future healthcare applications.

3.2 The PACE Platform for CDS Applications

There are multiple limitations of existing clinical decision support tools. They are often based on AI/ML models, which have very limited explanatory power, suffer from overfitting and model bias, inconsistent and mutually exclusive data inputs derived from variable quality scientific literature, and which may change recommendations on being retrained even with minimal additional data. This inconsistency, lack of deterministic or explanatory output and inability to stably and accurately represent the non-linear effects of combinations of features significantly limits the regulatory approval and clinical applications of such approaches. In addition, the disease models used by such systems are usually built from literature and GWAS results, which are very likely to have significant inherent biases, inconsistencies, and omissions in complex diseases like endometriosis.

PrecisionLife’s PACE (PrecisionLife Analytical Constraint Engine) platform overcomes these limitations. Using an array-based logic approach [5,6] it constructs a representation of the problem space using formal logic and geometric operators. This ensures that all relationships (linear and non-linear) that may impinge on clinically relevant outputs are evaluated in the context of what we know of the complex multiple etiology disease model, i.e., in this case the outputs of the analysis of the UK Biobank dataset.

Based on checks for mathematical consistency and completeness, it guarantees logical consistency of the model itself and the deduced results to ensure the consistent, stable and complete answers required in a clinical setting.

The CDS tool is based on the PACE platform which is sketched in **Figure 1**. All observed relationships between the signatures, mechanisms and phenotypes are compiled into a compact normalized data format, where data normalization refers to an established, information science process of creating minimally redundant data tables and establishing referential integrity relationships that protect the data from inconsistent dependencies.

In PACE this data normalized structure thus represents all valid combinations of the input data, which can be automatically tested for logical consistency (inconsistency yields zero valid combinations). The compiled binary model produced by this compilation can then be used for run-time applications by PACE’s inference engine, where all conclusions from any assertion can be deduced in real-time.

Figure 1 – Compiler and run-time engine of the PACE platform. All rules or relationships and compiled into a data normalized and compact representation of all valid combinations, which can be accessed in real-time with very limited computer resources, e.g. on a mobile device, but still with completeness of deduction.

In summary, the major advantage of PACE for CDS applications is that all knowledge is represented by the disease model, which can be tested for consistency automatically. Thereby we can ensure the completeness of the data and the accuracy of deduced output, based on that data, at the point of care. With very large, conventional databases or representations of complex data it is very easy to generate things that are logically inconsistent.

3.3 Data-structures used by CDS Prototype

This section details the internal data structures and data objects used by the CDS prototype tool utilising the PrecisionLife PACE platform. This operates in the context of our disease model, including ultimately the mapping of features identified to genes and mechanisms.

In a clinically validated system (rather than this prototype) we would usually include only those disease signatures that have multiple replication evidence in 3 or more disjoint population datasets, where we have agreement about directionality of the signatures' effects, and where there is a significant body of clinically actionable literature supporting the genes to which they are mapped.

In the future we will add more features to the disease model, including phenotypic, outcome and clinical data used for stratification of the patients. This will add more dimensions and hence more complexity.

3.3.1 Disease signatures (SNP genotype combinations)

A disease-signature can be of any order n with $n \geq 1$, including single SNP genotypes where $n=1$ (e.g. GWAS SNPs). The SNP indices of the patient must match the indices used in the file. Thereby the tool can do a very fast look-up of matching signatures of the individual patient, even with a large number of signatures and SNPs. This can be carried out in real-time with limited computer resources.

Disease-signatures are represented as a collection of SNP genotypes. **Figure 2** illustrates a number of disease signatures, labelled NSTATE, each containing 2 SNP genotypes

NSTATE	
(381 1)	(16255 1)
(381 1)	(18155 1)
(381 1)	(11469 0)
(381 1)	(28328 0)
(1290 1)	(15549 0)
(381 1)	(35470 0)
(381 1)	(25667 0)
(3237 1)	(4607 1)
(381 1)	(17840 0)
(381 1)	(5670 1)

Figure 2 – Disease signatures are represented as a collection of tuples, with each tuple consisting of an index number (representing a unique SNP) and the genotype for that SNP (where 0 = homozygous major allele, 1=heterozygous, 2=homozygous minor allele). The table shows 10 disease signatures, one per row, these signatures each contain two-SNP genotypes (n -states, where $n=2$).

3.3.2 SNP to gene mapping

In the internal data representation, each row is a SNP and the one or more associated genes (if any) to which they map. A cascade mapping process was used to map all the critical SNPs identified in the validated disease signatures to the human reference genome (GRCh38) to give the best estimate of the gene(s) likely to be associated with the SNP, see Taylor et al. for more details [7].

SNPs identified in the coding region of a gene (or genes) were mapped directly to this gene and any remaining SNPs within 2kb upstream or 0.5kb downstream were mapped to the nearest gene(s). If there is uncertainty about a wide range of cells and tissues implicated in the disease etiology, genes assigned by either expression quantitative trait loci (eQTLs) or chromatin interaction (Hi-C) data would not specifically be prioritized for further analysis (as they would likely be in other indications) to avoid capturing any spurious associations from non-trait-related tissues or cells. Genes that could additionally be mapped using only eQTL or Hi-C data from the critical SNPs were observed. All possible combinations are represented explicitly, including SNPs that could not be assigned to a gene by location or known function.

3.3.3 Gene to disease mechanism mapping

Each row represents a gene and its observed role in one or more associated mechanisms of action (MoA) with their relevant links and explanations, where known. All valid combinations of gene to mechanism are represented explicitly, including genes without a MoA, although we would likely choose not to report output for these as they are not clinically actionable. The description fields in the data format makes it possible to add information about each gene, for example links to publications. These data will be updated on a regular basis as new validated genetic associations and clinical literature become available.

GENE	MOA	DESCRIPTION	REF1	REF1_LINK	REF2	REF2_LINK
gene1	moa1	description1	ref1_1	https://...	ref2_1	https://...
gene2	moa2	description2	ref1_2	https://...	ref2_2	https://...
gene3	moa3	description3	ref1_3	https://...	ref2_3	https://...
gene4	moa4	description4	ref1_4	https://...	ref2_4	https://...
gene5	moa5	description5	ref1_5	https://...	ref2_5	https://...
gene6	moa6	description6	ref1_6	https://...	ref2_6	https://...
gene7	moa7	description7	ref1_7	https://...	ref2_7	https://...
gene8	moa8	description8	ref1_8	https://...	ref2_8	https://...
gene8	moa9	description9	ref1_9	https://...	ref2_9	https://...
gene8	moa10	description10	ref1_10	https://...	ref2_10	https://...

Figure 3 – Representation of data structure connecting genes to mechanisms of action (MoA). Note it is a one-to-many relationship, where one gene may have one or more mechanisms of action. Each MoA is accompanied by a description and references to clinically actionable literature, i.e., well accepted mechanistic links to disease biology or symptoms, often from review articles.

3.3.4 Mechanism of action to risk mapping

Each row represents a MoA and the number of matching signatures separating low/moderate risk (RiskLimitModerate) and moderate/high risk (RiskLimitHigh). Moreover, there are extra fields to add descriptions and relevant links.

MOA	RISKLIMITMODERATE	RISKLIMITHIGH	DESCRIPTION	REF1
moa1	1	3	description1	ref1
moa2	1	3	description2	ref2
moa3	1	3	description3	ref3
moa4	1	3	description4	ref4
moa5	1	3	description5	ref5
moa6	1	3	description6	ref6
moa7	1	3	description7	ref7
moa8	1	3	description8	ref8
moa9	1	3	description9	ref9
moa10	1	3	description10	ref10

Figure 4 – Representation of data structure holding thresholds for evaluating MoA risk.

The RiskLimit thresholds are based upon the observed distribution of disease signature counts associated with that mechanism in an endometriosis cohort (i.e. UKB in this case), as shown in **Figure 5**. We compared alternative cut-offs for stratifying 'high risk' and 'low risk' patients based on disease signature counts and evaluated the odds ratio and Fisher's Exact Test p -value for each high- vs low-risk comparison.

Figure 5 – Violin plot showing distribution of MoA relevant disease signatures used for thresholds for evaluating MoA risk. The dotted line shows the standard 25th percentile cutoff typically used in diagnostic applications.

The simple signature count approach is a crude approximation of overall risk as it implicitly assigns the same effect size to all signatures. However, with just the UK Biobank data to base this model on, this also reduces the risk of overfitting the risk score algorithm to the original UK Biobank cohort, which could result in poor predictive value in other disjoint patient cohorts such as CHB and other clinical populations.

Patients with a high number of signatures associated with a mechanism are classified as 'high risk'. Patients with a notably low number of signatures associated with a mechanism are classified as 'low risk'. Patients with 'moderate' risk have disease signature counts that are close to the mean for the population. In a final application the disease protective signatures would also be considered in evaluating a patient's actual risk.

3.3.5 Data used to populate the CDS prototype

An analysis of an endometriosis dataset derived from the UK Biobank (see 2 above) was used to provide realistic, but not necessarily definitive data, on which to test the CDS prototype, as this was the only dataset available to the PrecisionLife team.

A cascade mapping process was used to map all the SNPs identified in the disease signatures to give the best estimate of the gene(s) likely to be associated with the SNP in the human reference genome (GRCh38) as described above.

3.4 Risk Scores – Prototype Programs

The following software programs are implemented to support risk scores as described in Task 4.4:

1. **CDS Generator:** Compiles the PACE model (files .amb and .aml) representing all relationships between signatures, SNPs, genes, disease mechanisms, and thresholds for 'low risk', 'medium risk' and 'high risk'. Data flow diagram is shown in **Figure 6**.
2. **CDS Test:** Generates a JSON file reporting the risk profile of the individual patients, with explanations of matching genes and mechanisms and a radar plot image showing interacting mechanisms. Data flow diagram is shown in **Figure 7**.

Figure 6 – Data flow diagram of CDS generator (compilation of relations into PACE model)

Figure 7 – Test of the individual patient using CDS Test software.

3.5 Test of Patients in UKB

To illustrate as an example, we used the selected signatures from Task 4.2:

- 184 signatures
- 317 SNPs
- 69 genes
- 7 mechanisms of action (MoA)

We allow for multiple functions in the gene to mechanism mapping, to allow different pathways to be represented. The estimation of high, medium and low risk for each mechanism is derived from the RiskLimit thresholds discussed above. Below we provide some illustrative examples of the output of the CDS system when applied to the genotypic profiles of endometriosis patients from UK Biobank across the 6 main mechanisms of action that were identified by that dataset’s analysis.

Patient 1 (top left) has a notably high number of SNPs functionally annotated to genes that are associated with cell adhesion, cell differentiation, and cell migration in their genetic risk profile and none associated with ovarian cancer.

Patient 2 (top right) also has an excess of genes associated specifically with cell differentiation but no enrichment of genes associated with cell adhesion or cell migration.

Patient 3 (bottom left) has a very broad risk profile reflecting an enrichment of genes associated with several distinct MoAs, including cell adhesion, cell differentiation, central nervous system, and inflammation.

Finally, Patient 4 (bottom right) is unique in that their risk profile suggests an enrichment of genes associated with ovarian cancer, with only moderate enrichment in genes associated with cell differentiation.

Figure 8 – Radar plots summarizing observed disease mechanism risk factor profiles for four endometriosis patients. The central axis (hexagon) on the radar plot indicates 'low risk', followed by 'medium' and 'high'.

When applied to and replicated in multiple broader cohorts, these results can be used to identify subgroups of patients with different mechanistic aetiologies. As is happening with other diseases, this could inform the development of future diagnostic tools and/or more targeted treatment strategies.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, we have successfully implemented a prototype of a CDS tool to demonstrate how we can provide insight into the genetic risk profile of the individual patient, based on SNPs, associated genes and disease mechanisms. The patient’s mechanistic profile is transparent and explanatory with relevant links to genes and mechanisms, and the radar plots give a visual overview of the most important mechanisms involved. Future development using different parameters for case definitions, genetic risk prediction, and functional inferences with further real-world datasets is needed to explore accuracy and clinical utility.

The CDS prototype can be used to visualise mechanistic annotations of SNP genotype combinations (disease signatures) of any order n , as well as isolated SNP genotypes from GWAS. The PACE software platform underpinning the CDS prototype is designed for various data types and can be extended with non-genetic data in the future, for example proteomics, phenotypic or clinical data if required at the point of care.

5 Future Work

Post-FEMaLe, PrecisionLife plans to develop its CRS algorithm using multiple additional endometriosis datasets as well as exploring the functionality of the CDS prototype tool in phenotypically and ancestrally diverse, multi-omic datasets, and testing the robustness of output given different, ever-improving, annotation resources.

Figure 9 – PrecisionLife's mechanistic test workflow

Following the generation of results for a patient, clinical reports are generated by PACE and are in use by clinicians to understand the presentation of complex disease biology and adjust patients' treatment regimens.

6 References

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